

Multi-sentence and multi-intent classification using RoBERTa and graph convolutional neural network

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1. Introduction

Citation context analysis (CCA) is a crucial task in scientometrics analysis, examining how and why researchers discuss each other's work in their papers (White 2004; Teufel et al. 2006). Despite its long history, traditional CCA frameworks often make simplistic assumptions, focusing on a single sentence for analysis. This approach overlooks important phenomena, as a research paper frequently contains an extensive discussion of referenced research paper that span multiple sentences and convey multiple intents simultaneously. Consequently, relying on a single citation sentence to capture intent falls short, missing out on many other nuanced discourses. When an author cites another research article, it is often with one or more intentions, such as extending an existing study, utilizing developed methods, data, or approaches, among others. Citations are also crucial for establishing the hypothesis and building the foundation of the literature. It aids in understanding the rationale behind the work & prior contributions in the field. Additionally, citations are helpful for authors to convey how the proposed approach is different from the existing work (Lauscher et al. 2021). In the existing study of citation context analysis, we observed that authors mainly focus on a hard-coded window-based citation context around citing sentences (Athar and Teufel 2012; Ravi et al. 2018; Vyas et al. 2020). This limited approach fails to provide a comprehensive understanding since there may be preceding or following sentences that discuss the same citing paper with different intentions. Consequently, a single-sentence context is insufficient for thorough citation analysis (Budi and Yaniasih 2023). To overcome the limitation posed by a single citation sentence or a fixed window of citation sentences, we advocate to consider multi-sentence-based citation context along with its potential intents (Jurgens et al. 2018). Consequently, we considered analysing a citation context window of variable length and respective intents. As one citation context window can have multiple intents, we considered intent classification as a multi-label classification task. This study can be useful in various scientometric analysis tasks, such as citation search, citation recommendation systems, and citation scoring systems. Examining multi-sentence-based citation context can pave the way for new opportunities and challenges within the scientific citation analysis task.

Recently, Graph Neural Network (GNN) based architectures has gained much attention for different text analysis tasks. They are known for their capabilities in predictive and generative modelling (Scarselli et al. 2009). GNN can combine the strengths of transductive learning and generative learning. Moreover, transductive learning,

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a hybridization of transfer learning and inductive learning, is highly capable of handling complex natural language processing (NLP) tasks (Henaff et al. 2015; Defferrard et al. 2016; Hamilton et al. 2017; Li et al. 2018). Generative learning, on the other hand, is well-suited for training machine learning models in domains with limited labelled data. In this study, we employed GNN-based architectures to perform multi-label citation intent classification in scientific articles. The proposed approach can overcome the limitations of single-sentence and single-label citation analysis to model realistic citations. Throughout the process, we made the following contributions to scientometrics analysis.

- We proposed two novel GNN-based architectures viz. CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT for multi-label intent classification. CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN is a hybridized model combining RoBERTa (Robustly optimized Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers approach) and a graph convolutional network (GCN). CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT integrates RoBERTa with a graph attention network (GAT) together. The proposed architectures outperformed the baseline approach for citation intent classification.
- We considered to experiment with MultiCite dataset (Lauscher et al. 2021) multi-sentence and multi-intent classification analysis. It is developed by labelling 11,251 citation contexts considered from 1200 scholarly articles. To the best of our knowledge, we could not find any other human annotated dataset for citation context length analysis and citation intent classification.
- To determine the optimal context length for a citation window, we also performed context lengths analysis by experimenting with single-sentence context, three-sentence context, five-sentence context, seven-sentence context, nine-sentence context, and gold context.
- As Lauscher et al., (2021) did not provide explicit datasets for obtaining different context length-based datasets, it was very challenging to replicate their experiments. To overcome this issue, we considered certain punctuations and special symbols to delineate one or more sentences and citation context. This allowed us to develop and publish our [processed datasets](#)[§], facilitating the replication of experiments and benefiting the research community in advancing this area further.

These contributions will be quite useful in the understanding and modelling of realistic citation contexts along with respective intents. Furthermore, these would also be helpful in development of qualitative citation analysis.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 delves into a review of related work. In section 3, we present our two novel GNN-based architectures for multi-label classification, namely CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT. Section 4 outlines the specifics of the data used, and the experimental setup employed. Section 5 presents results and discussions. Finally, section 6 concludes the paper along with future directions of research in this area.

2. Literature Survey

In this study, we align with the common practice of using the terms “citation purpose”, “citation function” and “citation intent” interchangeably, as we observed this trend among authors. Citation context analysis involves various tasks, including citation function analysis (Teufel et al. 2006; Su et al. 2019), citation provenance analysis (Su et al. 2019), citation intent identification (Cohan et al. 2019; Motrichenko et al. 2021; Hu et al. 2022), and citation sentiment classification (Athar 2011; Xu et al. 2015). However, our focus in this research is primarily on two pivotal citation analysis tasks: citation intent classification and citation sentiment (polarity) analysis. Given our emphasis on citation intent classification, we conducted a survey of key studies in this domain, along with a review of relevant research in citation sentiment analysis.

Abu-Jbara et al., (2013) performed three tasks related to citation analysis viz. citation context detection, citation purpose detection, and citation polarity determination. For experiments, they considered 30 papers from the ACL Anthology Network corpus and extracted a window of four sentences around each citation. Jurgens et al. contributed to the field of citation function analysis by creating a dataset derived from 52 ACL papers, encompassing 1969 citations and references (Jurgens et al. 2018). The dataset constitutes 1021, 365, 344, 98, 73, and 68 samples belonging to background, motivation, uses, extension, comparison or contrast and future function, respectively. They reported a macro F1 score of 53.0%. They also proved different hypothesis related to a

§ <https://github.com/kravi2018/CiteIntentBERTGCN>

scientific article like (i) the citation placement within the same section of a research article might have different weightage unlike (Bertin et al. 2016), (ii) similar venue type have similar distributions of citation framing, (iii) increasing the number of workshops around same topic would have similar citation framing to their main conferences, (iv) topic diversity, uses, and compare & contrast are having top-most impact to future work, and (v) the number of uses citations reveal the rapid discovery science behind a particular area. Author (Motrichenko et al. 2021) employed SciBERT to experiment with two citation intent classification datasets viz. ACL-ARC** (6 classes, 1941 instances) and SciCite†† (3 classes, 11020 instances) and obtained a macro F1 of 72% and 85.5% for ACL-ARC and SciBERT respectively. They considered hand generated features suggested by (Jurgens et al. 2018) of a vector of length of 56 and generated a vector of same size for each paragraph for SciCite dataset.

Mercier et al. (2021a) proposed XLNet based ImpactCite to perform citation intent and sentiment classification. Citation intent based SciCite dataset comprising three classes viz. result, method, and background having 1491, 3154, and 6375 samples. On other hand, citation sentiment corpus clean (CSC-C) is having 829, 280, and 7627 samples belonging to positive, negative, and neutral classes, respectively. They achieved the macro-F1 of 88.93 and 77.73 for SciCite and CSC-C respectively. In an extension of prior research, author (Mercier et al. 2021b), conducted multi-task learning encompassing sentiment analysis and citation sentiment analysis. They utilized a modified XLNet to simultaneously learn distributions from features acquired from diverse sources such as movie and product reviews, Twitter data, and CSC-C. Training involved out-of-domain, sequential, and shuffled approaches across datasets from four domains. Despite these efforts, the highest macro F1 score of 88.93% was attained for the SciCite dataset when using single-task training exclusively.

Hu et al. (2022) addressed imbalanced citation intent classification using a bilateral-branch network having a set of common pre-trained vectors using SciBERT. The pre-trained vector was fed into two parallel layers: a shared layer, trained on both intent and auxiliary information (section title), and a non-shared layer, considering reversed sampling-based vectors generated from intent vectors to handle the imbalanced dataset. Additionally, a word attention layer was applied on top of these branches. They achieved an F-score of 25.45% on 50% of samples from the ACL-ARC dataset, which comprised 4000 samples. Lahiri et al. (2023) utilized prompt engineering for intent classification through zero-shot and few-shot learning. They employed the S2ORC (Lo et al. 2020) dataset to create a verbalizer. They obtained the best macro-F1 of 68.39% and 86.33% for ACL-ARC and SciCite dataset respectively in fully supervised setting. In a fully supervised setting, they achieved the best macro-F1 of 68.39% and 86.33% for ACL-ARC and SciCite dataset, respectively. Using zero-shot learning, they reported macro F1 of 53.86% for SciCite dataset only.

Yousif et al. (2019) performed a multitask learning for citation purpose classification and citation sentiment classification using a convolutional neural network (CNN) and recurrent neural network (RNN). These employed these architectures to extract extensive features automatically. Experimental evaluations on two public datasets demonstrated the model's superior performance compared to single task learning model based on support vector machine (SVM) and naïve Bayes (NB). Wang et al. (2020b) outlined their winning approach for the Citation Intent Recognition task in the WSDM Cup 2020. They focused on distinguishing between superfluous citations and genuine recognitions extracted from 62,976 description-paper pairs from 838,939 papers. They formulated the retrieval task as a binary classification task, which was mainly based on automated retrieval of relevant citation targets and extracting basic natural language-based, distance-based, and pairwise features. The models trained included Gradient Boosting Decision Trees, neural network models, and an ensemble of both. The final solution achieved a public score of 0.37458 and a private score of 0.3802.

In their work, Roman et al. (2021b) utilized various machine-learning techniques, including Linear Regression, Artificial Neural Network, K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Multinomial Naive Bayes (NB), applied to contextualized word embeddings for citation analysis. Their evaluation on two datasets, Sci-Cite and ACL-ARC, revealed that SVM achieved the best performance among the classifiers for both datasets. Roman et al. (2021a) introduced an automated approach to divide the whole research article into 3 categories: background, method, and result. They employed six ensemble methods by applying a word embedding and a clustering technique in tandem. The proposed approach was evaluated on the Sci-Cite dataset and achieving the highest F1 score of 81% through an ensemble of BERT & K-means. Additionally, they developed a novel dataset citation context dataset (C2D), comprising 10 million citation contexts.

Wang et al. (2020a) classified all cited reference into two categories namely important and non-important classification. They constructed different kinds of features related to each cited reference like bibliometric (number of citations per year, time distance, total number of citations, and shared authorship), syntactic features

** <http://jurgens.people.si.umich.edu/citation-function/>.

†† <https://github.com/se4en/scicite>.

(location of citation, citation length, and mentioned frequency) and contextual features (citation intent, textual similarity, and citation polarity). They applied statistical methods to identify significant features to apply three supervised classifiers namely SVM, k-nearest neighbours, and random forest. The evaluation was performed on two small datasets ACL dataset (Valenzuela et al. 2015) comprising 398 non-important citation vs. 67 important citation and Semantic Scholar dataset comprising 386 non-important citation vs. 72 important citation. They achieved F1 score of 85% on the first data using RF and 73% using SVM on the second dataset. However, the limited size of the datasets may impact the generalizability of the study's findings. Author performed sentiment classification the SciCite and the ACM dataset, consisting of 97 in-text citations (Visser and Dunaiski 2022). They achieved an F1-score of 69% using an ensemble of aspect-based sentiment analysis & BERT and 75% using BERT-cased, respectively. Additionally, they performed intent classification on the SciCite dataset and achieved an 85% accuracy using XLNet. Budi & Yaniasih, (2023) conducted experiments on 9173 citation sentences from five science disciplines: Food, Energy, Health, Social, and Computer. They employed a CNN-based multi-task learning approach for citation sentiment classification (positive, negative, and neutral), citation role classification (supplemental, result, method, and data), and citation function classification (introducing, relating, utilizing, explaining, and comparing). The reported F1 scores for these tasks were 78.33%, 90.75%, and 87.2%, respectively.

We examined a few additional studies that have some relevance to the analysis of citation intent. Dasigi et al., (2021) introduced an innovative method for the citation question-answering task. In their approach, they exclusively considered the title and abstract of the related paper, while the questions aimed to extract information from the entire text. Employing the Longformer-Encoder-Decoder (LED) on the Novel QASPER dataset, which consists of 5,049 questions from 1,585 papers, they achieved an evidence F1 score of 85.61%. Athar (2011) developed an annotated corpus of citation sentences and experimented with three citation polarities - negative, positive, and neutral. They employed different feature combinations viz. n-grams, specialized science-specific lexical features, dependency relations, sentence splitting, and negation features. Athar and Teufel (2012) experimented with four class annotation schemes viz. positive, negative, objective/neutral, and citation absent. They performed classification to detect sentiment and context window. They further experimented with 203,803 annotated sentences. These annotated sentences contain explicit mention of citations as 1509, 86, and 146 under objective, negative and positive categories, respectively.

Ravi et al., (2018) use ensemble method feature generation. The generated features are considered to classify article citation corpus using different architectures of CNN and long-short-term memory (LSTM) for citation sentiment analysis. They employed deep neural networks that were trained on the word vectors obtained on the input corpus. Ikram and Afzal (2019) aspect-level citation sentiment detection, focusing on 203 aspects related to scientific literature such as study, results, findings, research, hypothesis, etc. The approach involved considering opinion words, including verbs, nouns, and adjectives, around the selected aspects. Sentiment scores for each opinion word were retrieved from SentiWordNet (Esuli and Sebastiani 2006) to determine the overall polarity of each citation sentence. The experimentation involved a dataset from (Athar 2011) and 4182 samples (702 positive, 308 negative, and 3172 neutral) from (Xu et al. 2015), achieving an F1 score of 83.9% for the former dataset. Kilicoglu et al., (2019) performed citation on a dataset from (Xu et al. 2015) using SVM, CNN, and Bi-LSTM. They reported the best macro-F1 of 75.7% using CNN with parts-of-speech, dependency, and hand-crafted features. Aljuaid et al., (2021) conducted citation sentiment analysis by integrating cosine similarity score and sentiment score, employing various classification algorithms including SVM, KNN, NB, MNB, and logistic regression. The experiments were conducted on a subset of data referred to as D1 from (Xu et al. 2015), as well as a self-developed dataset named D2, comprising 282 citations. The reported best macro F1 scores were 66% for D1 and 56% for D2. While the study provided results, it lacked a comprehensive explanation of the experimental setup, including details on data distribution across different classes, the number of features considered for different experiments, and other relevant information. Yang et al. (2023) present the word-concept heterogeneous graph convolution network (WC-HGCN) model, which improves short text classification by enabling interaction between words and concepts using graph convolution networks. They tested on seven short text datasets reveal that WC-HGCN surpasses recent baseline models in performance. Zhao et al. (2024) introduced a novel Transformer model designed for extreme multi-label text classification (TLC-XML) comprising three main modules: Partition, Matcher, and Ranker. The Partition module creates label clusters based on semantic relationships, the Matcher uses GCNs to identify cluster correlations for improved classification, and the Ranker enhances predictions by considering label interactions. TLC-XML demonstrated state-of-the-results on some benchmark datasets.

Based on our literature review, we can observe that there is a significant gap between the current literature on the analysis of citation context length and citation intent classification. Hence, our study aims to fill this gap by addressing both tasks simultaneously.

3. Proposed Approach

This section is divided into three subsections. The first subsection presents an introduction to deep learning models like ROBERTA, GCN, and GAT to make this paper self-explanatory. The second subsection outlines the baseline approach, and while the third subsection presents our proposed approaches.

3.1 Deep learning models

As BERT, GCN, and GAT are major foundation models of our proposed approach. We presented a summary of these three deep learning models here.

3.1.1 Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT)

BERT is a widely used transformer model for language modelling. It performs bidirectional training on a transformer architecture using attention mechanism underneath. Instead of reading an input sequentially (either left-to-right or right-to-left), the transformer encoder in BERT reads the entire word sequence at once, making it bidirectional. This unique feature enables the model to comprehend the context of a word by considering its surroundings from both the left and right sides. Bidirectional training equips the language model with a more profound understanding of language context and flow. Since BERT's primary objective is language modelling, only the encoder mechanism is utilized. There are mainly two tasks, which undergoes during BERT pre-training:

- **Masked Language Model (MLM):** Before presenting word sequences to BERT, 15% of the words in each sequence are substituted with a designated [MASK] token. The model then seeks to anticipate the original values of the masked words, relying on the context offered by the remaining, non-masked words in the sequence.
- **Next Sentence Prediction (NSP):** In the BERT training process, the model is presented with pairs of sentences as input and is trained to predict if the second sentence in the pair directly succeeds the first sentence in the input document. In the training dataset, half of the inputs involve pairs where the second sentence is indeed the consecutive sentence in the input document. In contrast, the other 50% comprises instances where a random sentence from the corpus is chosen as the second sentence. This methodology assumes that the randomly selected sentence is unrelated to the first sentence, contributing to a diverse set of training scenarios.

BERT pre-trained models are **mainly available** in two sizes **viz. BERT_{Base} and BERT_{Large}**.

- BERT_{Base}: 12 layers, 768 hidden size, 12 self-attention heads, 110M parameters.
- BERT_{Large}: 24 layers, 1024 hidden size, 16 self-attention heads, 340M parameters.

We can choose either of them based on our requirements, availability of computational capacities, and suitability for a specific application.

3.1.2) Graph convolutional network

A Graph Convolutional Neural Network is specially designed neural network, which takes input graph-structured data in the form of adjacency matrix or list. It is very suitable for some applications like node classification, community detection, fraud detection, document classification and many more. The steps involved in GCN can be summarized as follows:

- **Graph Representation:** In a graph $G(V, E)$, nodes (V) represent entities and edges (E) represent relationships between entities. A_{ij} is an adjacency matrix having 1 or 0 or a real number. A non-zero value represents a connection between two nodes i and j .
- **Graph Convolutional Layer:** This layer aggregates information from neighbouring nodes by taking weighted sum of the nodes' vectors. A convolution operation over N neighbours of a node i can be represented using equation (1):

$$z_i = \sigma\left(\sum_{j=1}^N A_{ij} h_j W\right) \quad (1)$$

Here, z_i is the aggregated feature after one convolution operation, h_j is the feature/filter vector, W is the weight matrix, and σ is an activation function.

- **Stacking Layer:** Multiple graph convolutional layer can be stacked to capture complex relationships and higher-level features in the graph.

- **Node classification:** At L^{th} layer, *softmax* is applied to obtain probability distribution for class labels to perform classification task, as presented in equation (2)

$$Y = softmax(A.Z^{(L)}W^{(L)}) \quad (2)$$

3.1.3) Graph Attention Network

The Graph Attention Network overcomes limitations of GCN model by introducing masked self-attention layers. Using attention mechanism, it can assign different weights to neighbouring nodes. Attention mechanism prevents a neural network architecture to perform expensive matrix operations. GAT is suitable for inductive as well as transductive learning. It leverages one-hop neighbourhood to aggregate information for each node. GAT performs learning using following steps:

- **Node representation update:** The operation to be performed at a node i in layer l using equation (3):

$$h_i^{(l+1)} = \sigma(\sum_{j \in N_i} \alpha_{ij}^{(l)} W^{(l)} h_j^{(l)}) \quad (3)$$

where, $h_j^{(l)}$ is the representation of node i in layer l , N_i is the neighbourhood of node i , $\alpha_{ij}^{(l)}$ is the attention coefficient for the edge between nodes i and j in layer l , $W^{(l)}$ is the weight matrix for layer l , and σ is an activation function.

- **Attention coefficients calculation:** Calculate attention coefficients using a shared self-attention mechanism, as explained in equation (4)

$$\alpha_{ij}^{(l)} = \frac{\exp(LeakyReLU(\bar{a}^{(l)T} [W^{(l)} h_i^{(l)} || W^{(l)} h_j^{(l)}]))}{\sum_{k \in N_i} \exp(LeakyReLU(\bar{a}^{(l)T} [W^{(l)} h_i^{(l)} || W^{(l)} h_k^{(l)}]))} \quad (4)$$

Where: $\bar{a}^{(l)}$ is the shared attention weight vector, and $||$ denotes concatenation operation.

- **Multi-head attention:** GAT uses multiple attention heads to capture different aspects of relationships, as given in equation (5)

$$Head_i^{(l+1)} = \sum_{j \in N_i} \alpha_{ij}^{(l)} W_i^{(l)} h_j^{(l)} \quad (5)$$

- **Concatenation and Linear Transformation:** The outputs from different attention heads are concatenated and linearly transformed. Finally, classification is performed using *softmax* function.

3.2) Baseline approach

In our initial investigation, we adopted RoBERTa as the baseline model. RoBERTa stands out as a well-optimized variant of the BERT model, known for its improved performance. The fine-tuning process involved the models, and a mean over N binary cross-entropy losses was computed using equation (6)

$$L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N -[y_n \cdot \log \hat{y}_n + (1 - y_n) \cdot \log(1 - \hat{y}_n)] \quad (6)$$

with N as the number of classes, \hat{y}_n as the sigmoid activated output for class n, and y_n as the true label. Adam has used as optimiser (Kingma and Ba 2015).

Figure I illustrates the architecture of our baseline model, where we fine-tune a RoBERTa-Large model on the citation intent dataset, considering various context sizes. This baseline model serves as a reference for comparison and understanding the performance of subsequent models in the study.

Figure I: Citation context length analysis architecture (a) Document level full dataset, (b) Fixed context length datasets created from full datasets, (c) fine tuning a RoBERTa model on each of datasets, (d) Output layer as Sigmoid for multi-label classification.

3.3) Proposed approach

In this section, we present the working principles of two of our proposed approaches, namely, CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT.

3.3.1) CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT

In this research, the CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT model are proposed to perform citation intent classification using RoBERTaGCN and RoBERTaGAT respectively. Figure II illustrates the architecture of our CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN model, incorporating RoBERTa and GCN. The design of this architecture draws inspiration from Lin et al.'s work (Lin et al. 2021), specifically a model that integrates large-scale pretraining and transductive learning for text classification. RoBERTaGCN establishes a heterogeneous graph across the dataset, with documents represented as nodes utilizing RoBERTa representations. Through the joint training of the RoBERTa and GCN modules within RoBERTaGCN, this model capitalizes on the strengths of both approaches: large-scale pre-training, which benefits from extensive raw data, and transductive learning, enabling simultaneous learning of representations for both labelled training data and unlabelled test data by propagating label influence through graph convolution.

Figure II: CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN: Multi sentence multi label classification architecture (a) Input Dataset (b) Data transformation, graph generation, GCN, and GAT (c) Fine tuning ROBERTA model (d) Output layer as Sigmoid layer for multi-label classification (e) aggregating predictions of graph and ROBERTA

The initial step involved pre-processing and transforming the data to make it compatible for graph input. Subsequently, this prepared data was fed into a jointly fine-tuned RoBERTa and GCN model. Controlled aggregation of predictions from both RoBERTa and GCN was then performed. To regulate the contribution from each model, an interpolation parameter (λ) was introduced. This parameter allowed control over the percentage of predictions to be derived from RoBERTa and the percentage from GCN. The model underwent a fine-tuning process to determine the optimal value of λ that yielded the best results. In this design, we generate an interpolated final output by combining the outputs from both RoBERTa and GCN models. This interpolation process allows for a blended and optimized representation leveraging the strengths of RoBERTa and GCN. By replacing the GCN with the GAT model, we obtain the CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT model.

3.3.2) Graph construction

We construct a graph $G(V,E)$ comprising a set of vertices, V , and a set of weighted edges called E . Each vertex in V represents an embedding vector for either a word node or a document node. By drawing inspiration from TextGCN (Yao et al. 2018), we designed our architecture. We are having two types of edges based on a connection between a word node to word node (i.e word-word) and word node to document node (i.e. word-document). Accordingly, we define the weight of each edge. The weight for word-document edges is computed using the term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF). The weight of word-word edge, on the other hand, is computed using positive point-wise mutual information (PPMI). Hence, the mathematical formulation of weight computation for an edge between two nodes i and j is defined using equation (7).

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} \text{PPMI}(i, j) & i, j \text{ are words, } i \neq j \\ \text{TF} - \text{IDF}_{ij} & i \text{ is document, } j \text{ is word} \\ 1 & i = j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The PPMI value between two words i and j is computed as

$$\text{PPMI}(i, j) = \log_2 \frac{p(i, j)}{p(i)p(j)}$$

$$p(i, j) = \frac{\#W(i, j)}{\#W}$$

$$p(i) = \frac{\#W(i)}{\#W}$$

To train the GCN and GAT model, we need to represent each word and document in vector format. To provide each node as input to the GCN model, we use an input matrix $X = I_{n_{doc}+n_{word}}$ having the number of document nodes, n_{doc} , and the number of word nodes, n_{word} . The training and testing parts are obtained by splitting the input matrix X . Based on the input X , adjacency matrix A is derived and transformed into a weighted and normalized matrix \tilde{A} . At the i^{th} GCN layer, X is transformed as $L^{(i)}$ and computed using equation (8)

$$L^{(i)} = \sigma(\tilde{A} L^{(i-1)} W^{(i)}) \quad (8)$$

Where σ is an activation function, \tilde{A} is the normalized adjacency matrix and $W^{(i)}$ is the weight matrix at the i^{th} layer. At the 0th layer, X is the same as L^0 . The document vectors, word vectors, and weight matrix will be updated using pooling and stochastic gradient method. The final representations for documents and words are obtained at the end of the i^{th} layer, on which the sigmoid is applied to obtain the probability distribution of document labels, as expressed in equation (9)

$$Z_{GCN} = \text{sigmoid}(g(X, A)) \quad (9)$$

In this equation, g is a function representing the end-to-end GCN architecture. Cross-entropy loss over labelled document nodes is considered to estimate parameters of the GCN.

3.3.3) Interpolating RoBERTa and GCN Predictions

We feed the input matrix X into RoBERTa, which is then passed through a sigmoid function to obtain a probability distribution over document labels, as expressed in equation (10).

$$Z_{RoBERTa} = \text{sigmoid}(W, X) \quad (10)$$

Based on the probability distribution obtained from equation (9) and (10), we perform linear interpolation over Z_{GCN} and $Z_{RoBERTa}$ as presented in equation (11):

$$Z = \lambda * Z_{GCN} + (1 - \lambda) * Z_{RoBERTa} \quad (11)$$

Here, λ is varied in the range of $[0, 1]$ to balance the predictions from both models. In similar way, Z_{GCN} will be replaced with Z_{GAT} to obtain the class distribution for the class labels.

4. Experimental setup

In this section, we present dataset details, modelling environment details, and model evaluation measures.

4.1) Dataset Details

Lauscher et al., (2021) developed a MultiCite dataset, comprising 11,251 citation windows sourced from over 1,200 scientific research articles from computational linguistic area. This collection stands out as the most extensive compilation of human-labelled citation contexts to date. Notably, MultiCite includes citation contexts that span multiple sentences and carry multiple labels within the context of full paper texts. In the context of any citation sentence, there will be a minimum of two research articles under consideration, namely, the citing paper and the cited paper. The paper making the citation will be called the source paper, while the paper being cited will be identified as the target paper. We developed our dataset by considering manually labelled samples from MultiCite dataset, which is aka Gold Context dataset. Therefore, our dataset has seven different intent labels as provided in (Jurgens et al. 2018). The details of intent labels are presented in Table I.

Table I: Label details and distribution (Jurgens et al. 2018).

S#	Label Name	Label Details
1	Background	The contents considered from the target paper to present the foundation
2	Motivation	The source paper is motivated by the target paper
3	Uses	The source paper refers to ideas, methods, tools, etc. from the target paper
4	Extends	The source paper improves upon the existing ideas, methods, tools, etc., of the target paper
5	Similarities	There are similarities between the source and target paper
6	Differences	The source paper expresses some differences from the target paper
7	Future Work	The source paper cites the target paper in the future work.

We conducted two experiments, namely, (i) the analysis of citation context length using a baseline model, and (ii) multi-label intent classification. For the first experiment, we utilized six different datasets, as outlined in Table II (Lauscher et al. 2021). Hereafter, this dataset will be referred to as the *context length dataset*. Among them, the context windows were extracted to create five distinct training datasets with varying context lengths, including 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9. These context windows do not consider the real context around the citation sentence; instead, they involve an equal number of sentences before and after the citation sentence. The last dataset, 'Gold_context_sentence,' was prepared by a human annotator who considered the actual context around the citation context. During annotation, the annotator observed that the number of context sentences varied from 1 to 14 sentences. To determine the optimal number of citation context length, the authors opted to use an equal number of training, development, and test samples.

Table II: The context length dataset details (Lauscher et al. 2021).

Dataset Name	Context Length	Training (48.8%)	Development (21.75%)	Test (29.44%)
1_context_sentence	The context length of exactly one sentence	5491	2447	3313
3_context_sentence	The context length of exactly three sentences.	5491	2447	3313
5_context_sentence	The context length of exactly five sentences.	5491	2447	3313
7_context_sentence	The context length of exactly seven sentences.	5491	2447	3313
9_context_sentence	The context length of exactly nine sentences.	5491	2447	3313
Gold_context_sentence	The context length of varying number of sentences in the range of 1 to 14.	5491	2447	3313

For the second experiment, i.e., multi-label intent classification, the insights gained from the first experiment enabled us to determine that the '*Gold_context_sentence*' represents the optimal context length. Consequently, we derived five distinct test datasets from '*Gold_context_sentence*,' as outlined in Table III. Hereafter, this dataset will be referred to as *citation intent dataset*. Since Lauscher et al., (2021) did not explicitly provide datasets for citation intent classification, we made diligent efforts to replicate their process with the goal of obtaining a similar number of samples for different context lengths. However, we arrived at the given number of samples for the various datasets. The support size for each test dataset obtained through the baseline method and our approach is presented in Table III. Here, the support size denotes the number of samples extracted from '*Gold_context_sentence*,' encompassing varying context lengths such as 1, 2, 3, 4, and "All." Additionally, "All" refers to considering different context lengths ranging from 1 to 14. The distribution of the number of samples for "All" is as follows: 2784 for context length 1, 349 for context length 2, 110 for context length 3, 38 for context length 4, 22 for context length 5, 3 for context length 6, and 2 for context length 7 & 8. There is one sample each for context lengths 9, 10, and 14.

Table III. The citation intent dataset details

Test Dataset Name	The number of sentences taken from <i>Gold_context_sentence</i>	Test Data Support Size (Lauscher et al. 2021)	Test Data Support Size (Ours Approach)
Test1	1	2795	2784
Test2	2	335	349
Test3	3	112	110
Test4	4	39	38
Test5	All	3313	3313

4.2) Modelling environment details

For determining the context length, we opted to fine-tune hyperparameters for the RoBERTa model to replicate the results from (Lauscher et al. 2021). The number of epochs was explored in the range of [1, 9], the learning rate was set to either 1.00E-05 or 2.00E-05, and dropout values were considered from the range [0.3, 0.5]. In the case of citation intent classification, a grid search was conducted for the optimal GCN and RoBERTa learning rates, selected from the set {1.0E-03, 1.0E-04, 1.0E-05}, and the number of epochs varied within the range [5, 60] with an interval of 5. The effective batch size was set at 64, and a sigmoid prediction threshold of 0.5 was applied for both tasks. The balancing factor for both hybrid architectures was explored within the range of [0.2, 0.4]. In our experimental setup, we utilized a high-performance computing (HPC) machine, specifically a DGX node equipped with 8 GPUs. The hardware specifications included 2 x Intel Xeon Gold 6248 2.5G processors with 20 cores and 40 threads. The system ran Nvidia DGX Container Software to facilitate the seamless execution of the experiments.

4.3) Evaluation Measures

Two types of accuracies are computed in our evaluation:

Strict Accuracy: In this version, a prediction is deemed correct only if all predicted labels exactly match the true labels. Precision in this context requires an exact match of all labels.

Weak Accuracy: In the weak version, a prediction is considered correct if at least one of the predicted labels matches any of the true labels. This provides a more lenient measure, allowing for partial matches between predicted and true labels.

$$\text{Strict accuracy} = \frac{\text{Record count where all predicted labels match exactly the true labels}}{\text{Total records}}$$

$$\text{Weak accuracy} = \frac{\text{Record count where atleast one predicted labels match any of the true labels}}{\text{Total records}}$$

The weak accuracy assesses the best model's capability to identify any of the correct intents. This metric facilitates a comparison between our multi-label models and existing single-label models. Additionally, we offer a detailed breakdown of performance across various categories, categorized based on the gold context size.

5. Results and discussion

Table IV presents strict and weak accuracies for context length determination using RoBERTa large using training, development, and test partition provided for citation length dataset in Table II. We evaluated the performance of base model on datasets with varying context length, aiming to understand how the training context length impacts intent classification accuracy. We conducted various experiments, varying the learning rates for RoBERTa and adjusting the number of epochs during the model training. The optimal hyperparameter combinations, resulting in the best outcomes, are outlined in Table IV.

Table IV: The results for the *context length dataset*.

Epochs	3				5			
	1.00E-05		2.00E-05		1.00E-05		2.00E-05	
Learning rate								
Training Dataset	weak	strict	weak	strict	weak	strict	weak	strict
<i>1_context_sentence</i>	74.40%	62.80%	75.20%	63.50%	74.70%	62.00%	75.30%	62.10%
<i>3_context_sentence</i>	70.50%	59.20%	72.80%	60.90%	73.50%	60.00%	75.30%	60.20%
<i>5_context_sentence</i>	68.70%	58.00%	71.30%	60.30%	72.30%	59.20%	73.20%	59.50%
<i>7_context_sentence</i>	66.30%	57.00%	69.30%	58.40%	69.90%	57.80%	70.60%	58.20%
<i>9_context_sentence</i>	61.60%	52.90%	67.00%	56.00%	65.30%	54.00%	68.70%	55.00%
<i>Gold_context_sentence</i>	79.00%	66.00%	79.00%	66.00%	81.00%	66.00%	80.00%	66.00%

In the *Gold_context_sentence* dataset, we achieved the highest weak accuracy of 81% and strict accuracy of 66% with 5 epochs and a learning rate of 1.00E-05. For *1_context_sentence*, the top weak accuracy reached 75.3%, and the strict accuracy was 63.5%. Similarly, for *3_context_sentence*, the best weak accuracy was 75.3%, and the strict accuracy was 60.9%. As for *5_context_sentence*, the highest weak accuracy obtained was 73.2%, with a strict accuracy of 60.3%. For *7_context_sentence*, the best weak accuracy achieved was 70.6%, and the strict accuracy was 58.4%. Lastly, for *9_context_sentence*, the highest weak accuracy reached 68.7%, with a strict accuracy of 56.0%. Regarding the context size, weak accuracy tends to decrease with increasing context size due to the involvement of possible noise for each respective context size. Notably, the *Gold_context_sentence* consistently yielded the highest weak and strict accuracies. This suggests that providing a model with sufficient training data containing an ample number of context sentences can enhance its ability to grasp the nuances and pragmatics of citing intention more effectively. Based on the performance of the classifier for different learning rates and epochs, we can infer that changing either of them is not helping much for the given set of hyperparameters.

As we considered experimenting with a dataset derived from *Gold_context_sentence* for intent classification, we proposed two models, CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT, designed to build better-performing models for multi-sentence and multi-label intent classification. In our previous experiment with the base model, we achieved the best performance on the gold context dataset. Therefore, we utilized the pre-trained RoBERTa model on the gold context dataset to create new models in combination with two different graph neural networks, namely GCN and GAT. Table V presents the results obtained for the citation intent dataset to perform multi-sentence multi-label classification. As RoBERTa yielded the best performance in the previous experiments, we considered RoBERTa as the baseline model. The performance of CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN, CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT, and the baseline model across five test datasets is presented in the form of strict and weak accuracies. Considering multi-label classification, our intent was to increase strict accuracy. The best results for different models are highlighted in bold. These outcomes were achieved with hyperparameters set to a batch size of 64, GCN learning rate of 1.00E-03, and RoBERTa learning rate of 1.00E-05, an interpolation value of λ as 0.2, and a dropout value of 0.4 for CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN. CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT yielded the best results using $\lambda=0.25$ with a dropout of 0.6.

Table V: The results for *citation intent dataset*.

Test Dataset→		Test1		Test2		Test3		Test4		Test5	
Training Dataset↓		weak	strict								
1_context_sentence	Baseline	78%	69%	45%	28%	47%	24%	51%	18%	74%	62%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN	78%	72%	66%	52%	50%	36%	50%	33%	76%	65%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT	78%	72%	48%	38%	36%	36%	67%	33%	71%	53%
3_context_sentence	Baseline	74%	64%	59%	39%	54%	29%	62%	23%	72%	60%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN	84%	75%	45%	34%	36%	14%	33%	17%	82%	65%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT	84%	75%	48%	28%	22%	0%	50%	17%	64%	52%
5_context_sentence	Baseline	71%	61%	50%	33%	46%	27%	54%	18%	68%	57%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN	78%	72%	34%	24%	36%	14%	33%	17%	76%	71%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT	72%	69%	31%	28%	29%	14%	33%	17%	82%	76%
7_context_sentence	Baseline	62%	54%	43%	28%	48%	27%	51%	15%	60%	50%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN	50%	50%	41%	34%	29%	14%	33%	17%	6%	6%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT	47%	47%	38%	31%	50%	21%	50%	33%	47%	47%
9_context_sentence	Baseline	56%	50%	37%	25%	37%	21%	56%	18%	53%	46%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN	60%	50%	17%	9%	79%	43%	33%	33%	35%	35%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT	59%	47%	13%	7%	57%	36%	50%	33%	60%	24%
Gold_context_sentence	Baseline	80%	70%	68%	46%	66%	39%	64%	26%	78%	66%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN	59%	53%	62%	52%	85%	50%	33%	17%	88%	82%
	CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT	75%	69%	62%	52%	64%	36%	16%	7%	94%	88%

For the Test1 dataset, CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT achieved the best weak and strict accuracies of 84% and 75%, respectively. These accuracies are 10% and 9% higher, in terms of weak and strict accuracy, compared to the baseline method when training is performed on the same dataset. Even when considering the best performance of the baseline approach across different training datasets, our models still achieved 4% and 5% higher weak and strict accuracy. In the case of the Test2 dataset, the baseline model outperformed by 2% in terms of weak accuracy, while both our models yielded 6% higher strict accuracy, which is particularly noteworthy. For the Test3 dataset, CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN demonstrated splendid performance by achieving 19% and 11% higher weak and strict accuracy, respectively. Once again, our model showed better weak and strict accuracy for the Test4 dataset by 3% and 7%, respectively. Finally, we achieved state-of-the-art performance using CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT for the Test5 dataset, with results being 16% and 22% higher in terms of weak and strict accuracy, respectively. In terms of selecting a training dataset based on context size, we observed that the '*Gold_context_sentence*' yielded better performance for 3 out of 5 test datasets. Hence, combining context sizes of different lengths appears to be a better approach for performing citation intent classification.

When it comes to model selection, we recommend using CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT, as it achieved either equal or better performance for 3 datasets compared to CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN. Since it seems challenging for any model to exceed 88% strict accuracy, considering this as a threshold could be a viable measure for determining the best model for scientometrics analysis. Based on our experimentation, we concluded that CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT is the best model. Upon observing its strict accuracy across different test datasets, we noticed that the higher the context length of the test data, the lower the performance for all training context lengths except for '*Gold_context_sentence*.' That is why, combining all training data of different context lengths in '*Gold_context_sentence*' resulted in better results compared to individual context lengths. In terms of training context length, increasing the training context length making citation intent classification a difficult task. It might happen due to involvement of more noise in higher context length. As interpolation value of 0.2 and 0.25 yielded the best performance, it helps us to deduce that the contribution from RoBERTa is only 20% to 25% in final citation intent classification. Hence, the major contribution factor is obtained from GCN and GAT in final output. It indicates further that sharing semantics among different sentences using pooling and convolution is useful in citation intent detection.

6. Conclusions and future directions

In our initial study, we implemented a baseline model on citation context datasets to evaluate the impact of citation context length on citation intent classification. We fine-tuned the RoBERTa large model using datasets with varying context lengths. Notably, we observed a significantly higher accuracy on the gold-context dataset compared to the accuracy on the 1 or 3 or 5 or 9 -sentence datasets. This finding leads us to the conclusion that a more extensive corpus encompassing diverse context sizes proves more effective in capturing intent than single-sentence contexts. Our proposed hybrid architectures namely, CiteIntentRoBERTaGCN and CiteIntentRoBERTaGAT outperform baseline models for citation intent classification and achieved up to 6% higher weak accuracy and 22% higher strict accuracy for the largest test dataset. The enhanced performance attributed to shared semantics across different documents and words through graphical convolution and attention mechanism. Furthermore, we also derived that intent detection becomes challenging as the training or testing context window length increases.

For future work, we aim to modify existing architectures for increased accuracy, develop richer citation datasets with multiple sentences and multi-labels, create tools for assessing citation effectiveness using qualitative measures rather than simple citation counts, and develop a citation recommendation system for scientific articles based on our proposed architecture. Additionally, other cutting-edge deep learning methods will be incorporated on top of the fine-tuned model with the aim of further enhancing its performance. This approach would reflect an ongoing effort to leverage the latest advancements in deep learning to optimize the model's effectiveness in citation intent classification.

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